

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NABITAKA****FIRST NAME: LINDA****PROGRAM CODE: DARM****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. How would you describe academic writing?

- Academic writing is any writing produced as part of academic work. It seeks to provide answers to hypotheses and communicate ideas based on evidence.¹**
- It is fiction.
- It does not necessarily have formal prose.
- It does not need citations and references to other works as it is independent work.

2. Some of the critical rules while writing include:

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University), 7.

Writing should be clear, with short sentences, and short paragraphs. Paragraphs should be less than twenty lines with a sentence connecting one paragraph to another.²

There is no need to support any assertions with evidence.

It is best to use passive statements and repetitions to make it clearer.

Including sweeping generalities and leading the reader is acceptable.

3. What are the aims of a research project?

Asking a question that is worth answering, finding answers that are supported with good reason, finding reliable data that can support your reasons, and then drafting an argument that makes a good case for your answer.³

Does not involve collecting good-quality data.

A researcher's claim does not have to be supported by reasons and evidence as long as they are well-written.

In research, you always aim to find an answer to your question.

4. What should be included in citation information?

Citation information includes who wrote or assembled the work; that is the author, editor, or translator, what identifies the source; that is the title, page

² Ibid., 13-14.

³ Kate L. Turabian, Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, Ninth edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 23-24.

- number, volume number, issue number, or edition number, who published the source; place of publication and when it was published.**⁴
- When citing an online source it is not important to include the URL and date accessed.
 - The publisher's name is not included in a citation.
 - It is not necessary to include the year of publication in the citation.
5. How does one construct a plausible argument in research?
- Start by stating and evaluating a claim. The claim should have an answer that is significant and raises the interest of readers. Support it with reason and evidence. Then establish the relevance of your reasons.**⁵
 - Even without evidence one can state their claim and present it as research.
 - A researcher should not be bothered with the reader's questions or responding to them as long as they have written their research paper according to guidance.
 - In research one can state their claim without explaining the reasons for it.
6. When presenting data graphically the following is true of the different graphic presentations:
- Tables are best used when presenting trends.
 - Line graphs emphasize values and create strong visual contrasts.
 - Pie charts emphasize individual numbers and force readers to infer relationships.

⁴ Ibid., 44.

⁵ Ibid., 51-53.

- Bar charts emphasize comparison at a glance. They create strong visual contrasts away from individual cases.⁶**

7. When using the author-date type of citation

- When citing a book, include the author's last name, author's first name, year of publication, the title of the book subtitle of the book, both in italics, the place of publication, and the publisher's name.⁷**
- It is used most widely in humanities and social sciences.
- In Parenthetical citation, include all the author's names without the relevant page numbers.
- When an article is cited, the title of the article and sub-title are underlined.

8. How can you guard against misleading your readers when citing sources?

- When you quote, paraphrase, or summarize, be sure to capture the context and record the author's line of reasoning. The reader may want to see how it emerges from the argument and the argument supporting the conclusion should also be captured.⁸**
- When quoting a claim, it is not important to take note of the original role whether it was a major or minor point.

⁶ Ibid., 87-103.

⁷ Ibid., 229-230.

⁸ Ibid., 51-53.

If an author summarizes another author's views, they can be attributed to the author summarizing them.

It is not important to take note of why sources agree or disagree.

9. The notes-bibliography style of citation:

Is used mostly in natural and physical sciences.

A source is signaled by including the author and date in the text.

Cite the source of a quotation in a correspondingly numbered note that provides information about the source (author, title, facts of publication) plus relevant page numbers. Notes are placed at the bottom of the page (called footnotes) or in a list collected at the end of the paper or end of each chapter (called endnotes).⁹

Facts of publication are not enclosed in parentheses.

10. The following is true about writing a dissertation paper:

Only one manuscript can be created from a dissertation.

The title of the dissertation does not necessarily have to be consistent with the research questions.

It is not important to include all the elements of the research question in the introduction and the review of literature.

The literature review chapter provides the reader with a detailed and critical review of the literature that serves as the foundation for the dissertation

⁹ Ibid., 148-154.

research. It helps the reader to understand the variables that will be examined as well as provide a justification for the research questions.¹⁰

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¹⁰ Sampson, James P. 2017. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Ed. (Florida: Florida State University), 31.